

Table S1. Percent fatty acids composition of not-digested control (not treated) and treated fillets from seabass fed the different diets. Data are expressed as mol/100 mol FAMES and are means $\pm$ SD of 3 biological replicates. Statistical analysis was the one-way ANOVA using Tukey's as post-test. Different letters in the same row indicate statistical significance (at least $p < 0.05$).

Standard feed					
	Not treated	Brining	PEF	Brining + PEF	p value
14:0	3.31 $\pm$ 0.07 ^a	2.64 $\pm$ 0.24 ^b	3.21 $\pm$ 0.36 ^{ab}	3.46 $\pm$ 0.35 ^a	0.0322
16:0	19.78 $\pm$ 0.44 ^a	21.04 $\pm$ 0.86 ^a	19.97 $\pm$ 0.48 ^a	20.16 $\pm$ 0.38 ^a	0.1052
16:1 n-7	3.98 $\pm$ 0.28 ^a	3.71 $\pm$ 0.26 ^a	3.99 $\pm$ 0.21 ^a	4.75 $\pm$ 0.35 ^b	0.0096
18:0	4.15 $\pm$ 0.26 ^a	5.15 $\pm$ 0.06 ^b	4.25 $\pm$ 0.28 ^a	4.23 $\pm$ 0.35 ^a	0.0047
18:1 n-9	25.82 $\pm$ 0.78 ^a	24.25 $\pm$ 0.91 ^a	26.14 $\pm$ 1.51 ^a	26.04 $\pm$ 1.18 ^a	0.2180
18:2 n-6	9.69 $\pm$ 0.05 ^a	8.42 $\pm$ 0.10 ^b	9.63 $\pm$ 0.26 ^a	9.74 $\pm$ 0.57 ^a	0.0025
18:3 n-3	2.40 $\pm$ 0.10 ^a	2.07 $\pm$ 0.04 ^b	2.52 $\pm$ 0.13 ^a	2.48 $\pm$ 0.12 ^a	0.0027
20:1n-9	5.69 $\pm$ 0.13 ^a	4.89 $\pm$ 0.58 ^a	5.34 $\pm$ 0.81 ^a	5.97 $\pm$ 0.25 ^a	0.1401
20:4	0.98 $\pm$ 0.01 ^a	1.19 $\pm$ 0.11 ^b	1.05 $\pm$ 0.02 ^{ab}	0.97 $\pm$ 0.09 ^a	0.0194
20:5 n-3	6.78 $\pm$ 0.47 ^a	6.78 $\pm$ 0.39 ^a	6.71 $\pm$ 0.14 ^a	6.29 $\pm$ 0.30 ^a	0.3170
22:5 n-3	1.49 $\pm$ 0.04 ^a	1.42 $\pm$ 0.07 ^a	1.46 $\pm$ 0.02 ^a	1.40 $\pm$ 0.04 ^a	0.1547
22:6 n-3	15.92 $\pm$ 0.73 ^a	18.43 $\pm$ 2.11 ^a	15.72 $\pm$ 0.37 ^a	14.52 $\pm$ 1.72 ^a	0.0517
Innovative feed					
	Not treated	Brining	PEF	Brining + PEF	p value
14:0	3.12 $\pm$ 0.12 ^a	2.84 $\pm$ 0.20 ^a	2.88 $\pm$ 0.34 ^a	2.89 $\pm$ 0.27 ^a	0.5303
16:0	20.37 $\pm$ 0.21 ^a	20.36 $\pm$ 0.85 ^a	20.10 $\pm$ 0.64 ^a	20.54 $\pm$ 0.32 ^a	0.7287
16:1 n-7	4.42 $\pm$ 0.10 ^a	4.11 $\pm$ 0.14 ^a	4.30 $\pm$ 0.26 ^a	4.22 $\pm$ 0.09 ^a	0.2005
18:0	4.47 $\pm$ 0.15 ^a	5.00 $\pm$ 0.19 ^a	4.61 $\pm$ 0.55 ^a	4.90 $\pm$ 0.25 ^a	0.2385
18:1 n-9	30.14 $\pm$ 0.37 ^a	28.48 $\pm$ 0.47 ^a	29.03 $\pm$ 1.03 ^a	29.10 $\pm$ 0.46 ^a	0.0681
18:2 n-6	9.88 $\pm$ 0.24 ^a	9.63 $\pm$ 0.28 ^a	9.64 $\pm$ 0.41 ^a	9.57 $\pm$ 0.30 ^a	0.6500
18:3 n-3	2.44 $\pm$ 0.06 ^a	2.43 $\pm$ 0.09 ^a	2.42 $\pm$ 0.11 ^a	2.48 $\pm$ 0.14 ^a	0.8994
20:1n-9	4.85 $\pm$ 0.19 ^a	4.69 $\pm$ 0.34 ^a	4.65 $\pm$ 0.22 ^a	4.86 $\pm$ 0.04 ^a	0.5803
20:4	0.91 $\pm$ 0.03 ^a	1.04 $\pm$ 0.05 ^b	1.01 $\pm$ 0.06 ^{ab}	1.01 $\pm$ 0.02 ^{ab}	0.0273
20:5 n-3	5.69 $\pm$ 0.03 ^a	6.22 $\pm$ 0.51 ^a	6.18 $\pm$ 0.48 ^a	5.85 $\pm$ 0.11 ^a	0.3320
22:6 n-3	1.35 $\pm$ 0.04 ^a	1.30 $\pm$ 0.04 ^a	1.36 $\pm$ 0.09 ^a	1.31 $\pm$ 0.02 ^a	0.4872

22:5n-3

12.36 ± 0.50^a

13.90 ± 1.10^a

13.83 ± 1.34^a

13.27 ± 0.02^a

0.2182
